

1 **Genome Sequence Announcement of *Bacillus paralicheniformis* strain AA1**

2 Andrés Chávez-Almanza¹, Magda Armendáriz-Ontiveros², Jonathan Rojas-
3 Padilla¹, Ernesto Cantú-Soto¹, **Abel Verdugo-Fuentes^{1*}**

4 ¹ Departamento de Biotecnología y Ciencias Alimentarias, Instituto Tecnológico de
5 Sonora, 5 de febrero 818 Sur, CP 85000, Cd. Obregón, Sonora, México

6 ² Escuela Superior de Apan, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo,
7 Carretera Apan-Calpulalpan s/n, CP 43920, Chimalpa Tlalayote, Hidalgo, México.

8 ✉*abel.verdugo@itson.edu.mx

9 10 **Abstract**

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12 This paper presents the whole genome sequences obtained by whole-genome
13 shotgun sequencing of a *Bacillus paralicheniformis* species isolated from a milpa
14 producing system in the northwest region of Sonora, Mexico. This genome sequence
15 enhances the existing collection of genomics data and offers useful insights into the
16 bacterial diversity present in sustainable production systems. Furthermore, it
17 provides insights into key genes that are essential for their endophytic activities,
18 interactions with host plants, and efficacy in biocontrol against plant diseases.

19 20 **Introduction**

21
22 Bacteria are widely distributed in nature and are present in almost all terrestrial and
23 marine habitats, where they perform many different roles (Bahram et al., 2021;
24 Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2018). Within this group, a significant number of species
25 belonging to the genus *Bacillus* are commercially available biopesticides because of
26 the antimicrobial, nematicidal, and insecticidal compounds they generate (Fira et al.,
27 2018; Mnif & Ghribi, 2015; Poveda & González-Andrés, 2021). Plant defense
28 responses are triggered or intensified by *Bacillus* species, which confers plant
29 protection against pests and diseases (Dimopoulou et al., 2019; Pieterse et al.,
30 2014).

31

32 *Bacillus paralicheniformis* (Bp) has been extensively studied (Agersø et al., 2018;
33 Choyam et al., 2021; Du et al., 2019; Othoum et al., 2018). Bp possesses several
34 notable traits, including the capacity to generate antimicrobial bioactive substances,
35 promote plant growth, and thrive in challenging environments (Bokhari et al., 2019;
36 Sharma et al., 2019). In the field of sustainable food production, it has been
37 considered a biostimulant due to its potential applications in biotechnology and other
38 related fields (Du et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2022; Pellegrini et al., 2020). As a powerful
39 instrument in sustainable agriculture practices, microbial plant biostimulants (MPBs)
40 can boost crop yields and quality by stimulating several molecular and physiological
41 processes within plants (Bonini et al., 2020; Rouphael & Colla, 2020). Additionally,
42 MPBs are an efficient alternative to conventional phytohormone production in
43 industrial settings and can regulate plant physiological processes, which in turn
44 increase crop output and quality (Ben Mrid et al., 2021; Van Oosten et al., 2017).
45 This work focuses on the Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) of the bacterial strains.
46 WGS has several advantages, such as improved identification of bacterial species,
47 increased ability to detect genetic diversity, and higher predicting ability for functional
48 genes.

49

50 **Bacterial isolates**

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52 *Bacillus paralicheniformis* strain AA1 was isolated from a milpa production system at
53 the Technological Institute of Sonora in the northwest region of Sonora, Mexico. The
54 location is 27°29'46"N 109°58'18"W, and the elevation is 40 m above sea level.
55 During May, the area typically receives temperatures of 27.5 °C and an average
56 rainfall of 2.0 mm (Spark, 2021). During the vegetative phase of the maize growth
57 cycle in May 2023, three composite soil samples weighing about 1 kg each were
58 randomly obtained from three separate locations. The depth at which the samples
59 were collected was 20 cm. The soil samples were subsequently examined for
60 microbial analyses in the laboratory after being carried in a cooler maintained at 4 ±
61 2°C.

62

63 **Microbiological and genomic analysis.**

64

65 *Bacillus* isolation and purification were carried out in compliance with Elkhailil's
66 methodology (Mo et al., 2020). Ten grams of each sample were dissolved in 90 mL
67 of distilled water. The soil suspension was considered ready when heated to 80°C
68 for 15 min. After diluting the solution with sterile water, 0.1 ml of the mixture was
69 equally spread out on nutritional agar plates. The plates were then placed in an
70 aerobic incubator at 37°C for 24 h. The colonies were then prepared for microscopic
71 morphological identification using Gram staining and subjected to purification.

72

73 A DNA library was constructed using genomic DNA extracted from *Bacillus*
74 *paralicheniformis* strain AA1. Library sequencing was performed using an Illumina
75 NovaSeq sequencer. *De novo* genome assembly was performed using the SPAdes
76 genome assembler (St. Petersburg genome assembler; version 3.15.4) (Bankevich
77 et al., 2012). The genome of *Bacillus paralicheniformis* strain AA1 assembly yielded
78 48 contigs covering a total of 4,326,235 bp, with an N50 value of 701,491 bp and a
79 G+C composition of 45.85%. There were a total of 2,347 protein-coding sequences,
80 out of which 1,394 are hypothetical proteins, 136 are tRNA genes, and 6 are rRNA
81 genes. These results highlight the importance of this strain, and further research
82 could help us learn more about the bioestimulant effect of *Bacillus paralicheniformis*
83 strain AA1 in sustainable farming methods and its biotechnological potential.

84

85 **Data availability**

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87 The whole genome sequence was submitted to DDBJ/ENA/GenBank and assigned
88 the accession number JAYMDM000000000. The sequenced strain's BioProject
89 database accession number is PRJNA1061142. The project's Sequence Read
90 Archive information can be accessed using the accession number SRR27458597.

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